

NOTES

Indium (III) Chelate of Quinizarin-2-sulfonic Acid

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Received 5 June, 1971

Quinizarin-2-sulfonic acid forms coloured chelates with trivalent metal ions. It has been used as a reagent for aluminium¹. No systematic work has been done so far regarding its indium chelate. Indium forms a pink coloured chelate with quinizarin-2-sulfonic acid, having a molar ratio 1 : 1. The present communication deals with the composition, stability and structure as determined by U.V. and I.R. spectroscopy of this chelate.

Indium chloride (Schuchardt) solution was prepared and indium content was estimated by standard methods². Purified quinizarin-2-sulfonic acid (BDH indicator) was used for preparing a standard solution of the ligand. Hexamine perchloric acid buffer was used to adjust the pH of the solutions. Absorption measurements were made on a Perkin Elmer (Hitachi model 139) Uv-Vis- spectrophotometer using 1 cm. matched cells and I.R. spectra were recorded using Perkin Elmer (model 237 B) grating infra red spectrophotometer. The I.R. spectra were obtained using sodium chloride cells and the Nujol-mull technique. All the experiments were performed at 25°.

In aqueous medium indium quinizarin-2-sulfonic acid chelate showed a λ_{\max} at 490 nm. The effective pH range of the stable existence of the complex is 3.0–8.0. In this range the λ_{\max} of the reagent lies at 470 nm. pH 4 and wavelengths 540 nm and 560 nm were selected for further studies. The studies were made in very dilute solutions. The stoichiometry of the complex as investigated by Job's method, mole ratio method and slope ratio method was found to be as 1 : 1. The stability constant of the complex as calculated by mole ratio method and method using molecular extinction coefficient data comes to be 5.0 ± 0.05 and 5.10 ± 0.05 respectively. The average value of the free energy of the formation of the complex was found to be 6.92 ± 0.11 kcal.

The fact that the chelate is stable in solution at very low concentrations, was used for obtaining the chelate in solid form. 0.01 M solutions of metal and ligand were mixed in such a way that metal : ligand ratio was 1 : 3 and the final pH of the solution was adjusted at 5.0. The precipitate was washed with alcohol and benzene and dried. Analysis showed that the stoichiometry of the complex is 1 : 1. [Found In = 18.46%, S = 5.52%. In (QSA) \times H₂O requires In = 18.75%, S = 5.23%].

The I.R. spectra of the ligand and chelate were assigned the peaks by comparing them with that of the parent compound, quinizarin³. The I.R. spectra of the ligand and chelate showed the following peaks :

Peaks cm^{-1}		Assignment
Ligand	Chelate	
3350 (b, s)	3300 (m, b)	(-OH)
1626 (s)	1620 (w)	(C = O) free
1595 (s)	1585 (w)	(C = O) neighbouring sulfonic acid group.
1132 (m)	1125 (w)	(-OH)
1020 (m)	1025 (m)	-SO ₃ H vibrations
	825 (m)	Ambiguous
	710 (m)	(May be due to the coordination of water molecules.) (In-O).

Note : m = medium, s = strong, w = weak, and b = broad.

The shifting in both carbonyl frequencies gives rise to considerable ambiguity in deciding which of the carbonyls is involved in chelation. TLC does not reveal the presence of more than one chelate. So the structure of the chelate is one of the following :

I

II

The spectrum of the chelate shows a reduction in the intensity of the (-OH) band giving conclusive evidence for the involvement of only one hydroxyl group in chelation. Both the carbonyl frequencies are shifted towards longer wavelengths, so it is impossible to say exactly which of the hydroxyls is involved in chelation. Due to lack of force constant data in the literature it is not possible to carry out normal coordinate analysis to check our assignments. There is a peak at 880 cm^{-1} which does not appear in the ligand spectrum. This gives basis to the belief that this might be due to coordinated water molecules. The peak at 710 cm^{-1} has been tentatively assigned to the (In-O) mode as the region $600\text{--}800 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ generally exhibits Metal-Oxygen vibrational modes.

The authors are thankful to the Director of B.I.T.S., Pilani for the facilities provided and two of them (S.R. and C.S.G.P.) are thankful to C.S.I.R. for fellowships.

REFERENCES

1. E. G. Owens II and J. H. Joe, *Anal. Chem.*, 1959, **31**, 384.
2. L. Erdey, *Gravimetric analysis, Part II*, pp. 594, Pergamon, Oxford, 1965.
3. D. Hazdi and N. Sheppard, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1954, **50**, 911.